

SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT IN GLOBAL SCENARIO – KEY DRIVER OF WORK LIFE BALANCE

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Abstract

The paper presents a conceptual framework in the context of Knowledge Management (KM) in handling of work life balance issues. We believe that if the framework is adopted by any organization, it will yield more benefits to increase the quality of knowledge sharing. There has been indeed a paradigm way to balance the life in India. The new breed of strategies need to be efficient to tackle problems from cross functional, cultural and ethical perspectives and equipped with skills to benchmark for global leadership positions. There has been a crying need to usher in a quality movement and to benchmark the same with world standards. We have made an attempt to support our framework by analyzing one of the Knowledge Management tools that was implemented in India's Titanium equipment and anode manufacturing Ltd. (TEAM), (a pseudonym is given to mask the institution's name). This paper will review knowledge management (KM) literature that focus on KM issues, studies, and best practices surrounding the human & cultural elements involved in KM projects. This

paper defines a collaborative and learning culture, identifies issues that inhibit organizations to collaborate, and present best practices that organizations can use to help transform themselves.

Key words: *knowledge management, work life balance, collaborate*

Introduction

Effective knowledge management is now recognized to be 'the key driver of new knowledge and new ideas' to the innovation process, to new innovative products, services and solutions. Once we understand the value and benefits to be gained, we will then become far more motivated to look further at the implementation of knowledge management. It can be used to develop and apply knowledge management strategies to government, military operations, global poverty eradication, and international disaster management and even, now, knowledge management for global climate change. Knowledge management is applied today across the world, in all industry sectors, public and private organizations, humanitarian institutions, international charities and all the departments of the organization.

Man is very important resource which is living thing among the five M's. While new and innovative ideas and knowledge is implemented, employee will work with more fledged. Work is considered as a part of life. Recent findings in human resource studies have however shown that work and life could be two related but totally different concepts. Though separated by certain physical, psychological and temporal boundaries, the

two concepts are operationalized within the same context of time and space. The nature of work itself has changed from the 9-to-5 affair to a 24-hour, 7-day society, where customers expect services at times that suit them (CIPD, 2007). Technology, such as the cell phone, internet and other emerging gadgets, were expected to help alleviate this pressure and provide several options for “control and creativity in maneuvering the tenuous balance between work and family”(Temple 2009). The knowledge management is used as an effective motivational factor to balance the work and life very easily.

Knowledge management is a discipline which results in better achieving the individual objectives. The purpose of knowledge management must not be to just become more knowledgeable, but to create, transfer and apply knowledge with the purpose of better achieving objectives.

The conceptual framework of effective knowledge management

Now, the benefits of knowledge management for improved excellence, is simply ‘one side of the coin’. Effective knowledge management is accelerated knowledge creation and the driver for innovation. Increasingly, products and services are becoming ‘smarter’ and more knowledge based. Our ability to better collaborate in physical and virtual teams, as knowledge workers, is driving the process of new knowledge creation. Ideas can now be turned into innovative products and services much faster. As organizations are faster, individuals raise their accelerator. People are developing their competencies and confidence faster in organizations that practice effective knowledge management. All this

translates into human resource department paying more attention to the aspirations of every employee and creating parameters of social interactivity to enable them to constantly discover their true potential. Work-Life balance boosts productivity by teaching people how to attain a higher level of achievements & enjoyment every day, both on and off the job.

Knowledge management and work life balance in global scenario:

Our knowledge mantra is '**know and apply what you know the best, and link to the best of the rest**'

i. The key objective of Knowledge Management is to **enhance knowledge processing**. Organizations will have realized this objective when they should be correctly identify problems that need solving as they occur have robust information location and retrieval channels to enhance individual decision making embrace effective knowledge creation processes ensure that created knowledge is shared with and integrated across the whole of the organization.

ii. Methods that can help to achieve these goals include making better use of collaboration and communication tool, creating and promoting internal communities of practice, fostering the identity of virtual teams, using KM techniques such as Before Action Reviews (BAR), After Actions Reviews (AAR), pre-mortems, and retrospect during change activities, encouraging the use of a common language (e.g. corporate glossary, classification and/or taxonomies)

iii. Benefits of implementing effective Knowledge Management in organizational behavior include fully and accurately informed employees, clients, and stakeholders, improved team effectiveness and delivery of

outcomes, an organizational culture devoted to continuous improvement, an organization that is resilient and adaptable in the face of change

The benefits of knowledge management:

Effective knowledge management is used to reduce costs. Most individuals, teams and organizations are today continually ‘reinventing the wheel’. But as well as reducing costs, effective knowledge management is also increase our speed of response as a direct result of better knowledge access and application. Effective knowledge management, using more collective and systematic processes, will also reduce our tendency to ‘repeat the same mistakes’ so it is very easy to see how effective knowledge management will greatly contribute to improved excellence, which is to It reduce costs, Provide potential to expand and grow, Increase our value and/or profitability, Improve our products and service, Respond faster

REVIEW OF LIERATURE:

Sir John Steely Browne, BP, Harvard Business Review, 1997 argued that “Most activities or tasks are not one-time events. Whether it’s drilling a well or conducting a transaction at a service station, we do the same things repeatedly. Our philosophy is fairly simple: every time we do something again, we should do it better than the last time”. “Work”, according to Kuper and Kuper (1976) as quoted by Ogunbameru (2008) “refer to any physical and/or mental activities, which transform natural materials into a more useful form, improve human knowledge and understanding of the world, and/or provide or distribute goods to others”. It is “an instrument activity intended to provide goods and services to support life” (Edwards and Rothbard, 2000)

GlaxoSmithKline "The capabilities by which communities within an organization capture the knowledge that is critical to them, constantly improve it and make it available in the most effective manner to those who need it, so that they can exploit it creatively to add value as a normal part of their work"

Objective of the study:

- To know the importance and effect of applying knowledge management in work life balance.
- To analyze the reality while applying knowledge oriented service to workers to balance their personal life and professional life..
- In this study, the company has to identify the changes in the behavior of workers while processing new knowledgeable techniques during the operation.

Scope of Study:

The focus in this study is used to identify the relationship between implementing knowledge management and work life balance towards an India’s Titanium equipment and anode manufacturing Ltd. (TEAM), a pseudonym is given to mask the institution’s name.

Methodology:

The secondary data was collected to support our framework by analyzing one of the Knowledge Management tools that was implemented in India’s Titanium equipment and anode manufacturing Ltd. (TEAM), a pseudonym is given to mask the institution’s name. This date has provided

some of the HR policies and programs and its examples which is needed to employee for improvement of work commitment.

Data analysis:

This part focuses the pilot study of analyzing the response, while applying the knowledge management in workers as motivational factor.

Table: 1

The table shows the relationship between the two dependent variable of implementing knowledge management and work life balance towards an organizational activity.

Hypothesis:

H0- Implementing knowledge management does not has any relationship with the work life balance.

H1- Implementing knowledge management has significant relationship with the work life balance

Chi-square test = ——— Calculated value=8.88, Degree of freedom = (No. of columns - No. of rows)= (2-1)(2-1)=1 Table value of for 5 dft=3.84

Table:1 (analysis the relationship)

S.NO	LEVEL OF WORK LIFE BALANCE	ACHIEVING PRODUCTIVITY		Total	%	χ^2	df	Sig
		HIGH	LOW					
1.	HIGH	40	40	80	40%	16	1	3.841*
2.	LOW	35	85	120	60%			
Total		75	125	200	100			

O	E	O-E	(O-E)^2	(O-E)^2/E
40	30	-10	100	3.33
40	50	10	100	2.00
35	45	10	100	2.22
85	75	-10	100	1.33
200	200			8.88

Conclusion

Since the calculated value of is greater than the table value of , H0 is rejected 5%level. So, implementing knowledge management has significant relationship with the work life balance

Figure 1: The Correlation betweenimplementing knowledge management with the work life balance

Figure 1 Work life balance Vs quality management

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATION

- This case study indicates that knowledge management is used as motivating tool to employees to balance their life
- New techniques may cause the tremendous changes in the behavior of employees. It makes the employee to feel free from the work burden. So they have enough time to spend with their family.
- The continuous implementation of new strategies of knowledge management leads to effective performance towards an organization results high sales and more profit.
- Every organization needs to invest in creating and implementing the best knowledge networks, processes, methods, tools and technologies. This will enable them to learn, create new knowledge, and apply the best knowledge much faster.

- The company needs to induct the employee regarding the knowledge management which is the key driver of work life balance.
- We must all find a variety of strategies, both personal and professional, to assist us in negotiating this balancing act.
- We can aim to maximize the fit between ourselves and our jobs by looking for employers that offer the flexibility we need. We can also advocate for increased flexibility in our current jobs, understanding that we may or may not be successful.

Conclusion:

Knowledge has become the key strategic asset for the 21st Century .Every individual who wishes to successfully participate in the rapidly growing global knowledge economy must now consider the development of their personal knowledge management competencies as an ‘essential life skill’ for the 21st Century. This paper defines identifies issues that inhibit present best practices that organizations can use to help transform the inner problems of employee to best performance Many organizations are finding their knowledge management initiatives are failing to realize the promises for improved the work life balance through we can improve business performance and competitive advantage.

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